

Review Article

Male And Female Infertility Which Cause Child Birth Problem

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ABSTRACT

Men and women have different degrees of infertility. Experts say men and women are more likely to become infertile than women. Infertile men are at higher risk of having more children than women. Infertility can lead to miscarriage. Many of the risk factors for both male and female infertility are the same. Infertility in older women is most often brought on by fertility-related health issues. Smoking lowers the potential efficacy of reproductive treatments. radiation and chemotherapy may affect fertility. Caffeine intake may need to be restricted for women who are attempting to get pregnant. While regular exercise is vital, exercising to the point where your periods become irregular or non-existent can have an impact on fertility. Steer clear of excessive weight fluctuations. The copper T is used to Birth control, but there are drawback is its resist the vagina to kill the sperm or to stop growth of sperm. So that whenever the female have to birth child, its can't birth child because male sperm is kill or destroy by resistance of vagina.

INTRODUCTION

A birth defect is a problem that happens while a baby is developing in the mother's body. Most birth defects happen during the first 3 months of pregnancy. One out of every 33 babies in the United States is born with a birth defect. A birth defect may affect how the body looks, works, or both. Some case baby cannot growth and cannot birth. Because some female have infertility condition and other reproductive problem and infection or diseases.

Other case, we can also know that if male also have any type of reproductive problem such as nightfall while sleep, ejaculate daily sperm while removal from inside body. Or sexual contact in the age below 20 year age and other problem such as infections in scrotum or testis. So that sperm rate is decrease. That's why after the weeding life they cannot birth any child. Or some case child will birth after 5-7 year. Sometime after 10 year also, but some defects or problem in child.

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CHILD BIRTH PROBLEM CAUSE BY MALE INFERTILITY: There are various reasons child cannot birth because adults males:

- I. **Abnormal sperm production or function** due to undescended testicles, genetic defects, health problems such as diabetes, or infections such as chlamydia, gonorrhoea, mumps or HIV. Enlarged veins in the testes (varicocele) also can affect the quality of sperm.
- II. **Problems with the delivery of sperm** due to sexual problems, such as premature ejaculation; certain genetic diseases, such as cystic fibrosis; structural problems, such as a blockage in the testicle; or damage or injury to the reproductive organs.
- III. **Overexposure to certain environmental factors**, such as pesticides and other chemicals, and radiation. Cigarette smoking, alcohol, marijuana, anabolic steroids, and taking medications to treat bacterial infections, high blood pressure and depression also can affect fertility. Frequent exposure to heat, such as in saunas or hot tubs, can raise body temperature and may affect sperm production.
- IV. **Damage related to cancer and its treatment**, including radiation or chemotherapy. Treatment for cancer can impair sperm production, sometimes severely.
- V. **Some diseases which may affect male infertility**

Sr. No	Diseases
1	Epididymitis
2	Orchitis
3	HIV
5	AIDS
6	Gonorrhoea
7	Varicocele

CHILD BIRTH PROBLEM CAUSE BY FEMALE INFERTILITY: There are various reasons child cannot birth because adults female:

- I. **Ovulation disorders**, which affect the release of eggs from the ovaries. These include hormonal disorders such as polycystic ovary syndrome. Hyperprolactinemia, a condition in which you have too much prolactin — the hormone that stimulates breast milk production — also may interfere with ovulation. Either too much thyroid hormone (hyperthyroidism) or too little (hypothyroidism) can affect the menstrual cycle or cause infertility. Other underlying causes may include too much exercise, eating disorders or tumors.
- II. **Uterine or cervical abnormalities**, including abnormalities with the cervix, polyps in the uterus or the shape of the uterus. Noncancerous (benign) tumors in the uterine wall (uterine fibroids) may cause infertility by blocking the fallopian tubes or stopping a fertilized egg from implanting in the uterus.
- III. **Fallopian tube damage or blockage**, often caused by inflammation of the fallopian tube (salpingitis). This can result from pelvic inflammatory disease, which is usually caused by a sexually transmitted infection, endometriosis or adhesions.
- IV. **Endometriosis**, which occurs when endometrial tissue grows outside of the uterus, may affect the function of the ovaries, uterus and fallopian tubes.
- V. **Primary ovarian insufficiency (early menopause)**, when the ovaries stop working and menstruation ends before age 40. Although the cause is often unknown, certain factors are associated with early menopause, including immune system diseases, certain genetic conditions such as

Turner syndrome or carriers of Fragile X syndrome, and radiation or chemotherapy treatment.

- VI. **Pelvic adhesions**, bands of scar tissue that bind organs that can form after pelvic infection, appendicitis, endometriosis or abdominal or pelvic surgery.
- VII. **Cancer and its treatment**. Certain cancers — particularly reproductive cancers — often impair female fertility. Both radiation and chemotherapy may affect fertility.

RISK FACTORS

Many of the risk factors for both male and female infertility are the same. They include:

- **Age**. Age-related losses in women's fertility are noticeable, especially in the mid-30s, and beyond age 37, it declines quickly. Infertility in older women is most often brought on by the decreasing quantity and caliber of eggs, though it can also be brought on by fertility-related health issues. guys over 40 may have lower fertility than guys of earlier ages.
- **Using tobacco**. Both partners using tobacco or marijuana may lessen the chance of getting pregnant. Additionally, smoking lowers the potential efficacy of reproductive treatments. Women who smoke are more likely to experience miscarriages. Men who smoke are more likely to experience erectile dysfunction and poor sperm counts.
- **Using alcohol**. There is no acceptable level of alcohol consumption for women during pregnancy or conception. Alcohol consumption may be a factor in infertility. Heavy drinking can lower sperm count and motility in men.
- **Excess weight**. Being overweight and leading a sedentary lifestyle may raise the risk of infertility in American women. Being overweight might also have an impact on a man's sperm count.

- **Being too thin**. Women who have eating disorders, such as bulimia or anorexia, or who adhere to a very low-calorie or restrictive diet are at risk for having fertility issues.
- **Issues with exercise**. Obesity raises the risk of infertility and is a result of inactivity. Less frequently, ovulation issues in women who are not overweight may be linked to frequent, intense, rigorous activity.

SYMPTOMS

Not being able to get pregnant is the main sign of infertility. There might not be any other observable symptoms. Women who are infertile can experience irregular or non-existent menstrual cycles. Men who are infertile occasionally show symptoms of hormone imbalances, such as changes in hair growth or sex patterns.

PREVENTION

Some types of infertility aren't preventable. But several strategies may increase your chances of pregnancy.

Couples

For the highest pregnancy rate, engage in regular sexual activity multiple times around the period of ovulation. Your chances of getting pregnant increase if you have sexual contact at least five days prior to ovulation and for one day following it. For the majority of women, whose menstrual cycles are typically approximately 28 days apart, ovulation typically happens in the middle of the cycle, or halfway between periods.

Men

Although most types of infertility aren't preventable in men, these strategies may help:

- Refrain from using drugs, smoking, and consuming excessive amounts of alcohol, all of which may be factors in male infertility.
- Steer clear of hot tubs and hot baths because they can momentarily impair sperm motility and production.

- Preventing exposure to chemicals from the environment or industry, which may have an impact on sperm production.
- Limit prescription and over-the-counter medications that may affect fertility. If you frequently use any prescriptions, discuss them with your doctor; nevertheless, never cease using prescription drugs without first consulting a doctor.
- Workout in moderation. Regular exercise may enhance sperm quality and raise pregnancy success rates.

Women

For women, a number of strategies may increase the chances of becoming pregnant:

- **Stop smoking.** Not to mention your overall health and the health of a fetus, tobacco use has several detrimental consequences on fertility. Quit smoking if you're thinking about getting pregnant.
- **Steer clear of alcohol and illegal drugs.** Your ability to become pregnant and have a healthy baby may be affected by these chemicals. When attempting to conceive, avoid drinking alcohol and using recreational substances like marijuana.
- **Be cautious when drinking coffee.** Caffeine intake may need to be restricted for women who are attempting to get pregnant. Consult your doctor for advice on how to take caffeine safely.
- **Engage in light exercise.** While regular exercise is vital, exercising to the point where your periods become irregular or nonexistent can have an impact on fertility.
- **Steer clear of excessive weight fluctuations.** Infertility can result from hormonal imbalances brought on by being overweight or underweight.
- **Copper T.** The copper T is used to Birth control, but there are drawback is its resist the

vagina to kill the sperm or to stop growth of sperm. So that whenever the female have to birth child, its can't birth child because male sperm is kill or destroy by resistance of vagina.

CONCLUSION & DISSCUSION

Most birth defects happen during the first 3 months of pregnancy. A birth defect may affect how the body looks, works, or both. Some case baby cannot growth and cannot birth. Other case, we can also know that if male also have any type of reproductive problem such as nightfall while sleep, ejaculate daily sperm while removal from inside body. Or sexual contact in the age below 20 year age and other problem such as infections in scrotum or testis. Abnormal sperm production or function due to undescended testicles, genetic defects, health problems such as diabetes, or infections such as chlamydia, gonorrhoea, mumps or HIV. Overexposure to certain environmental factors, such as pesticides and other chemicals, and radiation. Damage related to cancer and its treatment, including radiation or chemotherapy. Ovulation disorders, which affect the release of eggs from the ovaries. Hyperprolactinemia, a condition in which you have too much prolactin — the hormone that stimulates breast milk production — also may interfere with ovulation. Uterine or cervical abnormalities, including abnormalities with the cervix, polyps in the uterus or the shape of the uterus. This can result from pelvic inflammatory disease, which is usually caused by a sexually transmitted infection, endometriosis or adhesions. Although the cause is often unknown,

certain factors are associated with early menopause, including immune system diseases, certain genetic conditions such as Turner syndrome or carriers of Fragile X syndrome, and radiation or chemotherapy treatment. Certain cancers — particularly reproductive cancers — often impair female fertility. Both radiation and chemotherapy may affect fertility. Many of the risk factors for both male and female infertility are the same. Infertility in older women is most often brought on by the decreasing quantity and caliber of eggs, though it can also be brought on by fertility-related health issues. Additionally, smoking lowers the potential efficacy of reproductive treatments. Women who smoke are more likely to experience miscarriages. Using alcohol. There is no acceptable level of alcohol consumption for women during pregnancy or conception. Being overweight and leading a sedentary lifestyle may raise the risk of infertility in American women. Women who have eating disorders, such as bulimia or anorexia, or who adhere to a very low-calorie or restrictive diet are at risk for having fertility issues. Obesity raises the risk of infertility and is a result of inactivity. Not being able to get pregnant is the main sign of infertility. Some types of infertility aren't preventable. For the highest pregnancy rate, engage in regular sexual activity multiple times around the period of ovulation. If you frequently use any prescriptions, discuss them with your doctor; nevertheless, never cease using prescription drugs without first consulting a doctor. Regular exercise may enhance sperm quality and raise pregnancy success rates. Not to mention your overall health and the health of a fetus, tobacco use has several detrimental consequences on fertility. Steer clear of alcohol and illegal drugs. Caffeine intake may need to be restricted for women who are attempting to get pregnant. While regular exercise is vital,

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